

RECURRENCE OF VARICOSE VEINS OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES. LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that due to the Countrymeters project estimates based on publications of the Population Division of the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan was 35,258,754 at the end of 2023. In addition, the number of residents of Uzbekistan is growing and in 2023 it increased by approximately 519,000 people [1]. Unfortunately, there are currently no well-designed studies and, accordingly, statistical data on the prevalence of varicose veins among residents of Uzbekistan. However, there is no reason to doubt that the incidence of this pathology should be similar to the incidence in other countries with a similar population composition. Accordingly, it is theoretically possible, with certain reservations, to calculate it quite easily. According to numerous data, in urbanized countries, at least 20% of the adult population suffers from clinically expressed (class C2 and higher according to CEAP) varicose veins [2–8]. Considering that approximately 25,900,000 adults live in Uzbekistan [1], it should be assumed that at least 5.2 million people suffer from varicose veins.*

Keywords: *endovenous laser obliteration, vein thrombosis, veins, external manifestations, thrombophlebitis.*

Varicose veins, left to their natural course, carry the risk of developing a number of complications in the form of trophic disorders, thrombophlebitis, deep vein thrombosis, bleeding from dilated veins, which not only lead to loss of ability to work, but are often also the cause of disability [9–15]. Conservative therapy for varicose veins does not eliminate either the cause or the manifestations of the disease, so effective treatment can only be achieved through surgical intervention [11,16–18]. However, even after surgical treatment, the frequency of relapses remains high, which, according to correctly collected data and statistics of large samples, exceeds 60% of cases in operated patients [19–23]. This gives rise to mistrust of surgical treatment in general and of modern methods in particular.

What is more important, the issue of relapses after endogenous laser obliteration is particularly relevant, since, on the one hand, before our very eyes this method has displaced combined phlebectomy from the pedestal where it had been for over a hundred years; on the other hand, unlike combined phlebectomy, this method has an additional risk factor for relapses [28].

2. The history of studying the causes of relapse of varicose veins of the lower extremities.

What is more important, the history of studying the causes of relapse of varicose disease and methods of their surgical prevention resembles the search for a "silver bullet" - an operation that will radically solve the problem and the disease will not return. Undoubtedly, such an operation should have eliminated not only the external manifestations, but also eliminated the cause of the disease [9,10,16,17,27].

In 1825, at the University of Venice, Dr. Tomasso Rima gave a lecture in which he demonstrated the reverse blood flow in the GSV in varicose disease. Several years later, he summarized his experience in an article entitled "On the immediate cause of varicose veins of the lower extremities, as well as on their radical treatment" [29]. In this article, Rima indicates reflux in the GSV as the cause of this disease and provides his data on its surgical treatment. This treatment consisted of ligation of the great saphenous vein. In 1846 in London, B. Brodie demonstrated that applying a tourniquet to the thigh distal to the saphenofemoral junction prevents blood reflux. Almost half a century later, after the introduction of asepsis and antisepsis, a similar test was used by Trendelenburg [30], who pathogenetically substantiated and popularized ligation of the GSV as a method of eliminating the cause of varicose veins - pathological reflux. This method quickly became famous among surgeons after Trendelenburg's article was published in 1890 [30]. The author himself knew about the need to interrupt the reflux in the GSV, but he did not understand where to ligate it. Based on this, the ligation was performed where it was more convenient for the surgeon - somewhere in the middle, or even in the lower third of the thigh. Such an operation did not eliminate reflux in the upper thigh, which led to the rapid appearance of a significant number of relapses, according to well-known data, their number exceeded half of all operations [31]. Meanwhile, the seed sown by Trendelenburg fell on fertile ground and 6 years later an article was published from Australia, in which Dr. William Moore proposed a modification of the Trendelenburg operation - ligation of the GSV "above all its tributaries on the thigh" from an incision parallel to the inguinal fold [32]. In essence, this was already a crossectomy in its modern form. It quickly became clear that it was necessary not only to eliminate the source of reflux – to ligate the GSV in the area of the terminal valve, but also to radically eliminate the routes of reflux propagation – to remove the great saphenous vein along with its dilated tributaries.

3 The era of "hyperradicality" in the treatment of varicose veins of the lower extremities.

Definitely, by the end of the 19th century, a theory had been formed in vein surgery, according to which relapses of varicose veins occur due to insufficient radicalism of the operation, when the surgeon forgot or did not consider it necessary to remove a vein and it became a source of relapse after a certain period of time. From this moment on, the word "radicality" acquired a special meaning in vein surgery. A long trend towards radicality began, which lasted for about a hundred years [9,33-35].

At the 13th surgical congress in Berlin in 1884, Madelung proposed removing the GSV from wide incisions [31]. Such an operation allowed for the most complete removal of the GSV and there was hope that this was the very radical operation after which there would be no more relapses. However, relapses continued to occur with approximately the same frequency as before, which caused more and more attempts to perform an even more "super-radical" operation. The champion in this race was undoubtedly the Rindfleisch operation. Its essence was that 3 to 5 spiral-shaped incisions of the skin and subcutaneous tissue to the muscle fascia were made on the shin, from the knee joint to the foot. In this case, all subcutaneous veins were intersected. The wound was tamponed in such a way that inflammation with suppuration developed in it, and it healed by secondary intention [36]. Rindfleisch and numerous followers of his method believed that rough spiral-shaped scars on the shin would not allow the superficial veins to recover and, accordingly, the reflux in them. And this would be the key to preventing relapses of varicose disease. By the first quarter of the 20th century, the "gold standard" for treating varicose veins was: ligation of the GSV directly in the area of the anastomosis, removal of the GSV trunk using Madelung or the

increasingly popular "American" method of removing the GSV using a W. Bebbcock probe [37]. Then Rindfleisch spirals were performed on the shin.

Besides that, in the "New Surgical Journal" for 1927, an article was published by the future professor, prominent surgeon, teacher and public figure, and at that time a young 28-year-old doctor N.I. Blinov [38]. The article summarized the experience of vein surgery accumulated by the end of the first quarter of the 20th century. The author analyzed the results of the operations described above, which at that time were the "gold standard" for treating varicose veins. He came to the conclusion that the frequency of varicose vein recurrence in patients operated on in their clinic was about 38%. The veins somehow "grew" and restored reflux through the rough scars of Rindfleisch spirals, which led to the inevitable conclusion that hyperradicality guarantees a high proportion of complications, while it does not particularly affect the percentage of relapses. Thanks to this and other works, hyperradicality was abandoned, but the trend of searching for a "silver bullet" for varicose veins remained.

Moreover, the article by N.I. Blinov, which drew a symbolic line under the era of hyperradicalism, pointed to the figure of 38% recurrence of varicose veins as a benchmark, which at that time was used as a starting point in the search for new ways of surgical prevention of disease recurrence.

4. Combined phlebectomy

However, in the first third of the 20th century, the Rindfleisch operation was abandoned, since it became the supplier of a large number of the most severe complications. By this time, the next "gold standard" of vein surgery had been formed, which was combined phlebectomy, consisting of a combination of 3 interventions: high ligation of the GSV in the area of the anastomosis, total extirpation of the GSV trunk to the ankle according to Bebbcock, and removal of varicose tributaries according to A. Narath [39]. In some cases, suprafascial ligation of perforating veins according to Cockett [40] or subfascial ligation according to Linton [41] was added to this.

In 1947, an article by R. Mcelwee et al. was published in which the authors graded the treatment results into 4 groups: excellent - in which patients had no complaints and no pronounced varicose veins; good - there were small recurrent veins that could be eliminated by injection techniques, relatively good, in which clinically pronounced varicose veins with corresponding symptoms appeared and very bad, in which progressive symptoms of venous insufficiency were added to all of the above. Patients underwent combined phlebectomy, the observation period was more than one year. Excellent results were obtained in 39% of patients. In the remaining 61%, recurrent veins of different sizes and prevalence were found [45]. In 1956, a group of American doctors from New York published a paper on the results of surgical treatment of patients with varicose veins since 1945 [46]. In total, the results of standard phlebectomy interventions of that time (crossectomy, stripping) on 646 limbs were analyzed; the results in some patients were followed up to 8 years. In 41% of cases, a relapse of varying degrees of severity was noted.

Additionally, in their article published in 1961, D. Brown et al. from Glasgow describe the results of a well-designed study. 100 patients with varicose veins (107 limbs) aged 15 to 69 years were randomized. The patients underwent crossectomy, which was supplemented by the introduction of a sclerosing agent into the GSV and incompetent perforating veins. The authors cite a 63% recurrence of the disease [47].

5. The era of phlebography.

It is known to everyone that in the middle of the 20th century, contrast phlebography began to gain momentum as a method of topical diagnostics of venous return disorders [48–50]. It would seem that such diagnostics would allow us to accurately determine the sources and routes of reflux and help identify obstructions of the main veins. Contrast phlebography became the foundation on which the formation and development of reconstructive surgery of veins took place. Thanks to it, it became possible to perform surgical treatment of patients with post-thrombotic syndrome, obstructions of the main veins [51,52]. However, quickly and imperceptibly, radiological methods shifted the focus of attention to the deep veins. Phlebography suspiciously often demonstrated reflux in the deep veins in patients with advanced forms of varicose veins [42,53–58]. It seemed that we were very close to understanding the causes of varicose veins and their relapses. Many methods for correcting deep vein valves appeared, both microsurgical and extravasal [49,53,56,57]. However, here again the eternal law of dialectics demonstrated its power: practice is the criterion of truth. Years passed, but not one of these methods lived up to expectations and did not enter into widespread clinical practice.

Moreover, this absence of deep vein surgery in widespread practice not only indicates that these methods are technically complex, but also that their results have not lived up to expectations [33].

6. Ultrasound diagnostics

In the last quarter of the 20th century, ultrasound methods began to be introduced into the diagnostics of venous diseases, which allowed not only to “separate the wheat from the chaff,” that is, to isolate the venous segments affected by reflux, thereby eliminating the likelihood that the surgeon would remove healthy veins and leave the affected areas [59–61]. The method raised the diagnostics of relapses of the disease to a previously unattainable height, especially early diagnostics, when reflux is already detected, but varicose veins are not yet present. The introduction of Doppler methods reversed the century-old trend towards radicalism and made the pendulum swing in the opposite direction: towards minimal invasiveness and vein-preserving surgery, when only the affected segments are removed based on a duplex study of the veins. Veins in which there is no reflux are preserved. Incidentally, it should be noted that after the introduction of duplex angioscanning, patients with reflux in the deep veins almost disappeared from their practice [62]. In 1986, at the dawn of the introduction of Doppler research methods in phlebology, an article was published [63] entirely devoted to relapses of varicose disease. The authors indicated that preoperative diagnostics using the new Doppler method gives more than encouraging results. This diagnostic improvement probably had an impact on the recurrence rate, and five-year follow-up after surgery showed that only 18% of patients required reoperation on recurrent veins. Importantly, in patients who underwent high ligation with sclerotherapy of the GSV trunk (as an alternative to its removal), the recurrence rate jumped to 41%.

7. Frequency of recurrence of varicose veins of the lower extremities after various methods of treatment. It should be emphasized that the immediate results of treatment of varicose veins are usually always good. Problems begin with time and the more time has passed since the operation, the worse the results [28,65–68]. Thus, in a study published in 2002, conducted in Finland, 8-year results were analyzed. All patients underwent preoperative marking with ultrasound examination. Of all those operated, 79% were asymptomatic and did not require further intervention on the veins. In 24% there were recurrent veins and reflux, which was confirmed by duplex examination. Recurrence was twice as common when the SPS was intact. Of all cases of recurrence, GSV above

the knee was 62%, SSV below the knee was 7%, recurrence in SSV was 16%, in the posterior accessory saphenous vein was 38%, and perforators of the thigh were 8%. In re-operated limbs, reflux occurred in 41% of patients [19]. This fact indirectly indicates that there is a certain group of patients with a permanent cause, in whom varicose veins recur again and again.

One of the most cited papers published in 2007 studied the 5-year results of combined phlebectomy with preoperative marking under duplex scanning control. It was shown that recurrences occurred in approximately 25% of cases. In 13% of patients, the source of recurrence was the SPS, and in 30% - the SPS [20]. In June 2013, a paper by Swedish researchers was published in which they analyzed the results of 10-14 years of observation of patients who underwent combined phlebectomy in combination with endoscopic dissection of perforating veins (SEPS). In 38% of patients operated on for varicose veins in the GSV basin, a relapse developed, the source of which was reflux in the SPS zone. It is important to note that in patients who were operated on for already developed recurrence of varicose veins in the SPS zone, recurrence developed again in 64% of patients. It is noteworthy that in patients operated on for varicose veins in the SSV basin, it developed in the same 38% of cases, and the source of recurrence was reflux in the SPS zone. In patients who were operated on for recurrence of varicose veins in the SPS zone, the dilation returned in 57%. With perforating veins, the situation was the opposite - 29% of relapses during surgery on the "primary" reflux and only 17% - with recurrent reflux through the perforating veins [21].

8. Classification of recurrent varicose veins of the lower extremities

It is worth mentioning that the most commonly used definition was adopted at the international consensus meeting held in Paris in 1998 on the topic "Recurrence of varicose veins after surgery" (REVAS). The definition indicated: the presence of varicose veins in the lower extremity previously operated on for varicose veins, with or without adjuvant therapy, which includes true recurrences, residual veins and new varicose nodes as a result of disease progression [24-26].

In 2009, new guidelines (VEIN-TERM) were adopted that defined recurrence of varicose veins, taking into account new data on the pathogenesis of this disease. According to VEIN-TERM [14], two terms were adopted for varicose veins detected after the intervention:

- 1) recurrent veins - those that appeared in the treatment area;
- 2) residual veins left after treatment.

The concept of PREVAIT was developed: PREsence of Varices (residual or recurrent) After operative Treatment) identified 4 main groups of causes of relapse and their definition, namely [14]:

Tactical errors - reflux persists in the GSV (SSV) due to incorrect diagnosis and the choice of an inadequate treatment method;

Technical errors - as a result of inadequate or inadequately performed intervention;

Disease progression - as a result of the natural course of varicose veins of the lower extremities;

Neovascularization - the appearance of small tortuous veins in the area of the ligated saphenofemoral junction, associated with varicose veins on the thigh.

Neovascularization should be mentioned here. These new veins appear in granulation tissue along the course of previously removed or ligated veins [24][71]. According to some data, neovascularization is responsible for the recurrence of varicose veins in 8 to 60% of cases

[22,69,71,72]. This problem has been actively discussed in surgical and phlebological circles, and even various methods of creating a mechanical barrier to neovascularization have been proposed, including the installation of silicone implants [73,74]. However, the problem of neovascularization has practically disappeared after the introduction of new, minimally invasive methods of eliminating reflux into clinical practice, primarily endovenous thermal obliteration [75].

9. Frequency of recurrence of vasculitis of the lower extremities after thermal ablation methods

In a prospective 5-year study of radiofrequency ablation for recurrence in the GSV basin, neovascularization was not detected. Thermal obliteration methods rarely lead to the formation of hematomas or leakage of endothelial cell factors, which can be a source of neovascularization [78].

These methods have another, no less significant problem - recanalization of the previously obliterated vein. After the introduction of certain obliteration methods into the clinic, the concept of "technical success" was born [79].

Definitely, technical success or failure means preserving the vein in an obliterated state in the postoperative period. Failure, accordingly, means recanalization.

Thus, in a randomized, very well-designed study, the results of two methods of thermal obliteration were compared - laser and radiofrequency ablation [80]. The results demonstrated a slightly higher technical success of RFA: 68 cases out of 70. With EVLO, this figure was close and amounted to 65 out of 68 cases.

One of the most cited studies by L. Rasmussen et al. on this issue showed a slight bias in favor of RFO - 100% technical success with RFA versus 143 out of 144 with EVLO. However, it should be mentioned that in this study, the author combined the results of EVLO with a "hemoglobin" and "water" laser, which was undoubtedly a planning error and could have led to such results [81]. A randomized clinical trial conducted and published by Shepherd et al., on the contrary, showed better technical results after EVLO: the number of technical successes to the total number of cases was 50/54. For RFA, this figure was 50/56 [82].

Malcolm Sydnor and a group of researchers from the University of Virginia, USA, published the results of a randomized trial comparing the results of using a 980 nm laser and ClosureFAST™ RFA. The authors demonstrated technical success in 72 cases out of 74. With EVLO, this figure was close and amounted to 77 out of 79 cases [83].

In general, it should be noted that by now the technical methods, speed and energy parameters of thermal obliteration have been so well-developed in practice that the technical results are very close to 100% and only some accident can cause vein recanalization after surgery [28].

Towards the end of the first quarter of the 21st century, non-thermal obliteration methods, in particular, cyanoacrylate obliteration [84–91], began to be rapidly introduced into clinical practice. These methods demonstrate very encouraging results. In particular, our Turkish colleagues from Ataturk University conducted a comparative study of laser and cyanoacrylate obliteration. For EVLO, the number of technical successes to the total number of cases was 203/204, while after glue obliteration, technical success was achieved in 100% of cases [92]. Despite all the unpleasantness of the situation, technical failure does not mean that in 100% of cases such patients will develop a relapse. At the same time, the absence of recanalization of the obliterated vein in no way guarantees against relapse [9,10,28,93]. In this regard, the results of well-designed randomized studies regarding the appearance of recurrent veins are interesting. In

2016, the results of a long-term, 6-year follow-up of patients after EVLO and phlebectomy in its classical sense (crossectomy + stripping) were published in the journal *Phlebology*. The authors convincingly demonstrated that in the long-term period there is no statistically significant difference between the number of cases of recurrent veins after different types of interventions [94].

In 2019 a comparative study of laser and cyanoacrylate GSV obliteration was published in the highly respected journal *Vasa*. The results demonstrated a lower rate of recurrence after glue obliteration: 2 cases out of 208 versus 5 out of 204 for EVLO (OR = 2.59) [92].

10. Recurrence rate of varicose veins of the lower extremities Cochrane review

In concluding the analysis of the incidence of varicose vein recurrence, it is necessary to draw a line. Undoubtedly, it was drawn by the Cochrane review published in 2021, which analyzed all randomized clinical trials known at that time regarding the elimination of reflux in the GSV. Foam sclerotherapy, a method that for many years was considered by almost all surgeons as the “worst” method of vein obliteration in the long term (more than 5 years), has proven to be quite comparable in terms of the number of relapses to the “most radical” method – combined phlebectomy in its modern version. After approximating all the results included in the review, sclerotherapy gives 41% relapses, and crossectomy + stripping – 38% (OR = 1.24) [79]. It is funny and sad that the same 38% of recurrent veins after the most radical operation on veins in the history of mankind (crossectomy + removal of the GSV + Rindfleisch spirals) was obtained by Dr. Nikolai Blinov when he was collecting material for his famous article, published in 1927, a hundred years ago [38].

11. Summary

By summarizing it should be mentioned that till present time the “true” cause of both the occurrence of “primary” varicose veins and its recurrence remains unexplored.

In conditions, where we cannot ensure recurrence-free disease after surgical intervention on varicose veins, minimally invasive methods of eliminating the already existing recurrence together with its source come to the fore.

The majority of varicose vein recurrences have their source in reflux through a long stump of the GSV and/or incompetent perforating veins. The methods available to the surgeon - sclerotherapy, laser, radiofrequency obliteration, non-thermal non-tumescent methods - either do not demonstrate reliable obliteration during long-term observation, or have limitations due to the anatomical features of the stump or perforators, as well as limitations associated with the technical design of the equipment and consumables for manipulations. Currently, there is a need to optimize existing methods of obliteration of perforating veins and the stump of the great saphenous vein in the complex treatment of recurrent varicose veins of the lower extremities. This encourages not only to clarify the causes of postoperative relapses of the disease, but also to search for and improve methods of their diagnosis, treatment and prevention.

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